

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

New Rotations: smarter cropping for healthier environments

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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Based on

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(Q1) Proposal name

New Rotations: smarter cropping for healthier environments

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This study will generate data over 5 years about the health of agroecosystems by quantifying how crop rotations affect soil, and beneficial and non-beneficial biota balanced against crop yield and stability using a combination of field, laboratory and in silico experiments.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

This project will generate quantitative, image and sequence data at field experiment plot resolutions including:

- **Agronomic management data and weather data.**
- **Time series UAV crop imagery.**
- **Soil properties data:** elemental content, nutrient availability, soil carbon fractions, pH, soil-pore structure imagery, and physical properties (e.g. texture, bulk density).
- **Crop data:** yield, yield traits, elemental content, nutrient use efficiency, and crop phenotypic traits
- **Biodiversity data:** manual invertebrate and botanical surveys
- **Disease incidence data:** manual disease scores for oilseed rape, oats and wheat
- **Microbiome sequence data:** generated from rhizosphere, soil, and air samples to identify microbial community phylogeny, structure, and function.

In addition, New Rotations will generate simulation data from statistical and process-based models plus associated code.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

Primary data will be generated from two large-plot field trials through direct field measurements and observation, and collection of soil cores for laboratory assays, sequencing, and X-Ray CT imaging. Weather data will be generated at 15-minute intervals to a data logger using an onsite weather station. Models will additionally combine primary data with publicly available data from the institute's Long-term Experiments (URL).

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

- **Sequence data** >15TB, saved as FASTQ formats.
- **UAV imagery data**: ~1TB raw imagery and transformed orthomosaics as TIFF and JPG formats.
- **X-Ray CT 3D imagery**: ~500 GB, raw imagery will be saved in TIFF format.
- **Quantitative data** extracted from UAV and X-Ray CT imagery will be stored as CSV.
- **Farm management and plot layout data** as JSON and GeoJSON respectively. ~1MB

All other datasets will be generated as tabular data and formatted as either CSV and Excel formats following Tidy Data principles. < 100MB

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

All data will be stored on local networked data storage with permissioned access. Raw data will be read-only and separated from curated/cleaned and analysis data. Networked data storage back-up and recovery is managed local IT Services.

Paper records (for example, for botanical surveys conducted in the field) will be scanned and the paper copies archived with local library services.

Example data standards expected to be used include: MIAPPE (plant phenotyping, and soils data miappe.org); MIMS (sequence data, pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18479204/); DarwinCore-Survey-Event (biodiversity data, ipt.gbif.org/manual/en/ipt/2.5/best-practices-sampling-event-data).

Source code will be managed using Github.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

Metadata standards used will be those stated. Core metadata describing the field trials in terms of cropping, management, experiment design and treatment factors, plus logged deviations, will be captured using FarmOS (local field experiment management software). FarmOS provides automatic ontological annotation of terms, for example plant experimental conditions ontology for annotating treatment factors.

Plots and samples will be allocated an IGSN (igsn.org) identifier. Each IGSN will provide plot or sample metadata and datasets will be expected to reference source IGSNs.

Methods and procedures will be documented using protocols.io and surveys and experiments recorded in

electronic lab notebooks, including details of capturing instrument metadata.

A curated variable list referencing public ontologies is maintained to ensure variables are consistently described and interoperable with other studies.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

The project's field trials are intended as long-term study sites therefore the value of the data is anticipated to increase over time. Tabular datasets relating to the field trial plots, including data extracted from source imagery, plus weather data, will therefore be retained indefinitely and loaded to an in-house Postgres database for long-term curation.

Datasets which will be retained for at least 10 years include: datasets used for analysis; raw UAV and X-Ray CT imagery; sequence data; source code will be retained for at least 10 years. Processed imagery may not be retained, but the code for generating processed imagery and extracted data will be. Raw imagery will be retained as new processing techniques may increase information extraction.

Sequence data will be retained locally for at least 10 years.

A local metadata catalogue will be used to index dataset locations, metadata, and responsible persons.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

Soil microbiome sequence data will be published to the ENA and analysed using MGnify (ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/). Soil sample metadata will be publicly accessible via locally hosted IGSN landing pages. Crop phenotyping and traits data, and soils data be published to either the institute data repository or NERC EIDC (eidc.ac.uk). Source code on Github will be published to the Zenodo repository.

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be collected over a 5-year period, therefore for each year's data there will be a 3 year period of exclusive use during which data will be embargoed, but metadata describing how data can be accessed for collaborative work during embargo periods will be published.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

Datasets will be published to publicly accessible data repositories listed (3.1) with a citable DOI, IGSN or

equivalent identifier and findable through indexing services such as Google Dataset Search. Datasets will be published under Creative Commons Attribution Licence conditions, and with sufficient metadata to describe their origin and use. Code will be published with an open source software licence. In most cases data will be openly accessible, the exception being large image data. In this case published metadata will describe how image data can be accessed.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

To ensure reusability, datasets will be formatted and described using relevant community data standards, as outlined. Where data standards do not exist, datasets will be described and annotated using relevant domain ontologies, made available using non-proprietary text formats, and structured following Tidy Data conventions.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

Other than the permitted period of exclusive use, there are no restrictions on data sharing.

(Q14) Secondary use

Data will be freely available, permitting reuse by the wider research community.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

The institute is Cyber Essentials Certified, and all staff are required to complete cybersecurity training.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

Security risks from bad actors are mitigated through secure IT infrastructures compliant with the UK Government Cyber Essentials. Electronic Lab Notebooks are CFR 21 Part 11 certified, ensuring full audit trails are maintained. Internally, access to shared data areas is permissioned, and all raw data and final analysis data is made read-only.

(Q17) Capabilities

As outlined in the JoR, this project has costed in Research Data Steward and Bioinformatics support to ensure research data management and sharing is effectively carried out. The project has access to core funded IT Services staff and infrastructures, including electronic lab notebooks.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

This is a large project involving multiple research groups using a common experimental site. To ensure good data management oversight, a designated research data steward will maintain a catalogue, based on the NERC full DMP template, of planned and in progress datasets, code, and samples which will be reported and updated at project meetings. This will record revisions to the original data management plan.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The institute has a Net Zero group aiming to reduce our carbon footprint and local IT Services are a key contributor to this.

(Q20) Responsibilities

- **Study-wide data management:** PI supported by designated research data steward
- **Metadata creation:** Individual researchers, guided by research data steward
- **Data security:** IT Services, all project members
- **Quality assurance of data:** Individual researchers, supported by research data steward